

Sensitivity analysis methodology to identify the critical material properties that affect the open hole strength of composites

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Abstract

Aeronautical industries are concerned about generating efficient and cost-effective statistical design allowables of composite laminate responses. Within this framework of uncertainty quantification and management (UQ&M), accounting for the various uncertainties is crucial to calculate the design allowables which, in turn, adds confidence to the design and certification process. In this context, as a precursor to UQ&M, we establish a global sensitivity analysis framework to identify the material properties that influence the laminate responses. In this study, an open hole tensile (OHT) test configuration is considered. In a first step, sensitivity analysis based on an analytical model is performed using Sobol, FAST, and Morris methods, whereas in a second step, sensitivity analysis based on a detailed 3D finite element model (FEM) incorporating damage is performed using Morris. The paper compares different sensitivity approaches in terms of computational cost and results. Further, different case studies (varied notched hole sizes, width-to-diameter ratios, laminate stacking sequences, etc.) are performed to study how the sensitive parameters vary for different configurations. The study identified the Morris method, along with the selected hyper parameters, as being suitable for FEM based sensitivity analysis due to its low computational cost.

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Five material properties (out of 23) were identified as influencing the open hole laminate tensile strength. Using the FE simulations performed for the Morris analysis, a first estimation of the design allowables (A and B basis values) on the OHT strength is also presented. The results from this paper contribute to the next step of UQ&M, where only the identified sensitive material properties can be considered for detailed experimental characterization or for building meta models to calculate the design allowables. A framework like this, complements experimental campaign to reduce the associated costs and knock-down factors, thus shortening the certification process.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Virtual testing, Design allowables, Uncertainty quantification, Finite element analysis

1. Introduction

Aeronautical industries are constantly faced with the challenge of accounting for the various uncertainties related to the response of composite materials. Uncertainties arising from material properties, manufacturing processes, test setups, data reduction methods, loading conditions, specimen geometry, laminate stacking sequences, manufacturing defects etc., can significantly vary composite structural performance. Hence, uncertainty quantification and management (UQ&M) methods [1; 2] are used to furnish the variability associated to each input parameter and provide the design allowables, thereby adding confidence and robustness to the design and certification process.

The standard approach of obtaining the design allowables is through experimental testing of 18 (termed as B18 reduced sampling) or 30 (termed as B30 robust sampling) specimens from three or five batches, respectively, to obtain the B basis design allowable [3]. This process is quite extensive and expensive as it covers the whole manufacturing and testing costs of the specimens. In addition, modifying the laminate layup, the geometry or the loading configuration requires the entire process being repeated. With the development of high-fidelity numerical models that can predict with good accuracy, industries have started to complement experimental tests with virtual tests to reduce the recurring and non-recurring costs, leading to greater freedom in the design space

19 and more efficient designs.

20 The failure strength of a composite laminate at the meso-scale depends on the mate-
21 rial properties of the fiber-matrix system, the laminate configuration, specimen geome-
22 try, etc. Material properties account for the elastic, strength, and fracture properties of
23 the inter- and intralaminar material system. These numerous properties are character-
24 ized using extensive laboratory tests to obtain the material card and are then used in
25 finite element (FE) simulations to predict the response of the composite laminates. FE
26 simulations account for the deterministic mean values of the material properties but do
27 not account for the variability in these material properties. However, in reality, compos-
28 ite laminate response can be significantly influenced by the variability of these material
29 properties. In this context, it is important to account for their statistical distribution
30 obtained from the experimental tests, which indeed demands extensive experimental
31 test campaigns. Hence, it is beneficial to understand which influential properties are
32 the ones that affect the laminate's response.

33 Global sensitivity analysis (GSA) is multi-disciplinary and is applied across various
34 fields to estimate the sensitive parameters that influence a target output response [4].
35 In the context of composite laminates and associated material properties, integrating a
36 sensitivity analysis into a composite laminate test campaign helps to screen the influ-
37 ential and non-influential material properties. Once the sensitive parameters have been
38 identified, the experimental tests to obtain these corresponding material properties can
39 be performed with greater care, ensuring that the associated uncertainty is minimal.
40 For example, for an interlaminar fracture toughness test, switching from a linear elastic
41 fracture mechanics (LEFM) based data reduction to a J-integral based toughness mea-
42 surement facilitates to avoid the high uncertainties associated with the measurement
43 of the crack length during the test [5; 6]. Further, within the framework of uncertainty
44 quantification, these selected key properties can be well characterized by increasing the
45 number of specimens to 18 or 30 (B18 and/or B30 sampling as recommended in the
46 Composites Materials Handbook CMH-17 [3]) to obtain a better statistical distribu-
47 tion. In addition, identifying the sensitive material properties can help towards more

48 efficient FE based optimization methods and/or generate meta models for machine
49 learning, where only the key parameters need to be considered to optimize the output
50 response. These numerous benefits substantially support the importance of performing
51 sensitivity analysis within the context of composite materials, with the aim of improving
52 the design of composite structures.

53 Notched strength of composite laminates is an important parameter in the aero-
54 nautical industry as it can be the limiting factor in the design of composite structures.
55 Open-hole strength testing of laminated composites is a good practical example and is
56 often employed as a baseline test to understand a material's structural performance [7].
57 This test is a characteristic test that has an interaction between geometric and mate-
58 rial properties. Further, the test replicates the scenario of fastener holes and cut-outs
59 which are commonly seen in composite structural components. Moreover, the open-
60 hole strength and the failure modes are strongly influenced by the different specimen
61 configurations (notched hole size, width-to-diameter ratios etc.) [7], and hence makes
62 it challenging and an optimum test to validate a sensitivity analysis case study.

63 Numerous researchers have investigated the open-hole tensile response of a compos-
64 ite laminate through experimental [8], numerical [9], and analytical methods [10]. For a
65 generic quasi-isotropic laminate, delamination and in-plane fibre failure are two damage
66 modes that lead to final failure. Hallet et al.[11], however, reported complex interactions
67 between the matrix cracks, fibre splits and delaminations during the damage process.
68 The failure stress and damage mechanisms vary significantly with different configura-
69 tions such as notched hole size [12], layup configuration [13], width-to-diameter ratios,
70 sub-laminate scaling [7] etc. Advancement in the FE numerical models ensured the
71 good predictability of not only the failure strength, but also the interaction between
72 the damage modes. These models are crucial for GSA and UQM approaches, despite
73 the hindrance of their heavy computational costs.

74 GSA has been widely used in different types of applications [14] and various review
75 papers have analyzed the different sensitivity methods and the feasibility in terms of
76 predictions and/or computational time [4; 15]. The choice of a sensitivity method de-

77 depends on various factors such as the: computational cost of a single model evaluation,
78 number of input variables, complexity of the model, allotted time for the project, etc.
79 [4]. GSA is generally broken down into the following methods based on regression,
80 screening, variance and/or meta model. For instance, variance-based methods decom-
81 pose the variance of the model output for every input, provides quantitative measures
82 but with the drawback of high computational cost. The screening-based method on
83 the other hand is optimum for models demanding high computational cost since these
84 methods require less model evaluations, but their drawback is that they provide only
85 the qualitative measures to rank factors and not quantify the effects of different factors
86 on the output. Vallmajó et al. [16] performed a local sensitivity analysis (LSA) on the
87 OHT strength using an analytical model and provided a UQM framework to obtain a
88 B-basis design allowable for notched composite parts. Cózar et al. [17] performed an
89 LSA on the projected delamination area of the impact scenario and on the compression
90 after impact strength of composite laminates using FE models. Further, only the sensi-
91 tive parameters identified were considered to build a response surface for calculating the
92 design allowables using UQM approach. Thapa et al. [2] performed uncertainty quan-
93 tification and a GSA (using polynomial chaos expansion based sobol indices) utilizing
94 a progressive failure analysis to obtain the key parameters for the tensile, compressive
95 and shear response of a laminate with a circular cutout. To the authors' knowledge, GSA
96 using high-fidelity FE models considering progressive damage for composite response
97 prediction has not been previously reported because of the complexity of the models
98 and the computational time required.

99 The main objective of this paper is to establish an economical and efficient global
100 sensitivity analysis framework in regards to the open hole tensile response of composite
101 laminates. This work demonstrates the material properties that can influence the open
102 hole strength of a notched composite laminate. In a first step, an analytical framework
103 based on OHT strength prediction is combined with different global sensitivity analysis
104 methods to identify the key material and geometrical properties. Three sensitivity
105 analysis methods (Sobol, FAST and Morris) methods were studied and compared for

106 a baseline configuration using an analytical model that has nine input parameters. In
107 the next step, using a detailed 3D FE numerical model that also accounts for inter- and
108 intra-laminar progressive damage, a sensitivity analysis using the Morris method was
109 performed to estimate the influential material properties, out of a total of 23 properties
110 accounted for, the ones that influenced material properties. In addition, different case
111 studies were performed where we varied the number of ply clusters, notched hole sizes,
112 width-to-diameter ratios and laminate stacking configurations were varied to study how
113 the influential material properties vary for different cases and to also validate the GSA
114 approach. Finally, a first estimation of the design allowables on the OHT strength is
115 also presented.

116 **2. Methodology**

117 *2.1. Open-hole tension: Analytical model*

118 Furtado et al. [10] proposed an efficient analytical framework that can predict
119 the notched strength of a multi-directional composite laminate using only three ply-
120 based material properties. The framework integrates a finite fracture mechanics model
121 [18], invariant based trace theory and master ply concept to estimate the stiffness and
122 strength [19; 20], and an analytical fracture mechanics model to estimate the laminate
123 fracture toughness [21].

124 The proposed analytical model only requires three material properties (the longitu-
125 dinal Young's modulus, E_{11} , longitudinal strength, XT , and the fracture toughness in
126 the fiber direction, G°), in addition to the laminate stacking sequence and the specimen
127 geometrical properties (width of the specimen, W , and the diameter of the hole, D) as
128 the input. Furtado et al. [10] compared the predicted notched strength (both tension
129 and compression load cases) from the analytical model with the experimental values
130 for different laminates and material configurations and obtained excellent correlations.
131 Interested readers are referred to [10; 18] for more details on the formulation of the
132 model.

133 *2.2. Open-hole tension: Numerical model*

134 We used a mesoscale FE model to simulate the open hole tensile response, where
135 Abaqus/Explicit 3D solid elements (C3D8R) were used to model the plies. The in-
136 terfaces were modeled using Abaqus finite thickness cohesive elements (COH3D8) [22].
137 Progressive intra-ply damage was accounted for with the continuum damage model pro-
138 posed by Maimí et al. [23–25]. The damage activation functions are based on LARC04
139 failure criteria. The predictive capability of the model has been demonstrated for var-
140 ious loading cases such as OHT [8; 26], double edged notched tension [8], impact and
141 compression after impact [25; 27–29]. The intralaminar model was implemented in a
142 VUMAT user-written subroutine. An intralaminar element was deleted once the fiber
143 damage variable (d_1) reached 1. Further details of the model can be found in the works
144 from Maimí et al [23; 24]. The simulations were performed in Abaqus using a dynamic
145 explicit solver without using mass scaling. A uniform in-plane element size of 0.5 mm
146 was used for all the elements (both inter and intralaminar) throughout the study. Each
147 ply was modeled as a solid layer with one element through the ply thickness, while the
148 thickness of the cohesive elements was set to 0.01 mm as recommended in the Abaqus
149 documentation [22]. Tensile load was introduced by applying a pre-defined displace-
150 ment at one of the specimen edges while keeping the other edge constrained. The pre
151 and post processing of the models were automated using python scripts and the final
152 failure (OHT load) is defined as the maximum load in the force-displacement curve
153 from the simulation.

154 *2.3. Sensitivity analysis*

155 In this work, we used three sensitivity analysis methods: Sobol [30–32], FAST
156 (Fourier Amplitude Sensitivity Test) [33] and MOAT (Morris One-At-a-Time) [34; 35].
157 Sobol and FAST are the two most commonly used variance-based methods. These
158 methods quantify the output variance for every input parameter and also calculate the
159 interaction effects among the different input variables. The Sobol method provides
160 the Sobol indices (SI) such as the first, second, and total order sensitivity indices as a

161 quantitative measure of the SA. The first order SI represents the main effect of each
 162 input variable on the output response, while the second order SI measures the effect due
 163 to the second-order interaction between two input variables. The total SI (introduced by
 164 Homma et al. [36]) denotes the effect due to an input variable and also its interaction
 165 with all the remaining input variables. The FAST method, originally developed by
 166 Cukier et al. [33], also computes the first and the total (developed in an improved
 167 version by Saltelli [37] as eFAST) order effects. Variance-based methods are efficient
 168 for complex and non-linear models but have a drawback of high computational cost.

169 MOAT is a screening-based one-at-a-time method where each parameter, x_i , is var-
 170 ied along a grid size of Δ_i to create a trajectory in the defined design space. For a
 171 model with n input parameters, one such trajectory contains n variations and $(n + 1)$
 172 model evaluations. In each model evaluation, only one input parameter is varied at a
 173 time. The elementary effect of the i th parameter can be calculated using:

$$EE_i = \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta_i, \dots, x_n) - f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta_i} \quad (1)$$

174 where EE is the ratio of the change in the model output to the input parameter varia-
 175 tion. Each input variable is varied across selected p levels in the grid space. The MOAT
 176 method uses hyper parameters r (denotes the number of repetitions/trajectories) and
 177 p (number of levels in the design space grid). The improved Morris sampling technique
 178 (proposed by Campolongo et al. [35]) provides a better scan of the input design space
 179 by finding trajectories with the maximum dispersion in the input space.

180 The Morris method provides two sensitivity measures: μ^* , which provides the overall
 181 influence of the input parameter on the output, and σ , which assesses the non-linear
 182 or interaction effect of that input parameter with the rest of the parameters. A Morris
 183 plot of μ^* vs σ qualitatively screens the various input parameters into: (a) insensitive
 184 (low μ^* and low σ), (b) with high influence on output but with less interaction/non-
 185 linear response (high μ^* and low σ), (c) with high influence on output as well as high
 186 interaction with other parameters (high μ^* and high σ) and (d) with less influence
 187 on the output but high interaction with other parameters (low μ^* and high σ). Note

188 that the Morris sensitivity measures cannot be compared quantitatively between two
189 different Morris plots. We used the open source Python library SALIB [38] to create
190 the input matrices and perform the sensitivity analysis.

191 In the whole process of GSA, the first step is to create sampling for a selected
192 sensitivity analysis method. The user defines the number of input parameters, their
193 bounds, sampling method, and the hyper-parameters depending on the GSA method.
194 Once the sampling is performed with input variations, then each row of the obtained test
195 matrix corresponds to one model evaluation (either using analytical or FE simulations).
196 The whole input matrix is run to obtain the output response (OHT strength in this
197 case). Along with the input and output matrix, GSA sensitivity analysis is performed
198 to identify the sensitive parameters depending on the corresponding GSA method.

199 3. Problem definition & Case studies

200 The OHT baseline case selected is a quasi-isotropic laminate ($[45/90/-45/0]_{3s}$)
201 with 24 plies of 0.131 mm per ply. The nominal laminate thickness is 3.12 mm. The
202 hole diameter is selected as 2 mm with the in-plane dimensions: 12 mm (width) and
203 24 mm (length), and maintaining a width-to-diameter (W/D) ratio of 6.

204 In the first step, global sensitivity analysis is performed on the OHT response pre-
205 dicted by the analytical model [10]. Table 1 presents the nine input properties (seven
206 material and two geometric properties) considered for the analytical model based sen-
207 sitivity analysis. The selected material is IM7/8552 and the mean (μ) and standard
208 deviation (σ) values were obtained from [39]. The material properties follow a normal
209 distribution and are varied within their 99.7% confidence interval (± 3 standard devia-
210 tions from the mean). Sensitivity analyses are performed with the three different GSA
211 methods explained above, with nine input parameters and the OHT strength as the
212 output response.

213 In the next step, we move from analytical-based GSA to FEM-based GSA to incor-
214 porate all the material properties associated to the OHT test. Table 2 presents all 23
215 material properties considered in the FEM model that are the input parameters that

216 account for the elastic, strength and fracture properties of both the fiber and matrix of
217 the material system. Morris SA is used in this step due to the expensive computational
218 time associated with the variance-based SA. Literature recommends the effectiveness
219 of MOAT to give satisfactory predictions with a reduced number of sample runs, which
220 applies in the case of FE-based SA [4]. The first objective is to select the Morris hyper-
221 parameters (number of trajectories r and number of grid levels p) and then use these
222 to study other configurations.

223 We set up different case studies associated with the OHT response to study the
224 change in the sensitive material properties, compared to the baseline case explained
225 above. The different case studies studied here are the effect of: (a) ply clustering, (b)
226 notched hole size, (c) width-to-diameter ratios and (d) laminate stacking configurations,
227 on the sensitive material properties that affect the OHT strength. Table 3 presents the
228 different laminates employed to study the effect blocked plies have. Laminate Lx1, Lx2
229 and Lx4 contain 1, 2 and 4 blocked plies, respectively, and are of the same laminate
230 thickness. Table 4 details specimens with different hole diameters to study the effect
231 of notched hole size. Specimen width and length and the hole diameter are varied by
232 keeping the W/D ratio as a constant value of 6. Table 5 introduces different specimens
233 with varying W/D ratios. WD-9, WD-6, WD-3 and WD-1.5 have W/D ratios of 9,
234 6, 3 and 1.5., respectively, which is obtained by increasing the diameter of the hole
235 and keeping the specimen width and length constant. Table 6 presents laminates with
236 different stacking sequence configurations such as quasi isotropic, a hard and a soft
237 laminate. The percentage of plies associated with each laminate is also mentioned in
238 the table.

239 [Table 1 about here.]

240 [Table 2 about here.]

241 [Table 3 about here.]

242 [Table 4 about here.]

243 [Table 5 about here.]

244 [Table 6 about here.]

245 4. Sensitivity analysis results: Analytical model

246 In this section, we compare the sensitivity results from three different SA methods
247 (Sobol, FAST and Morris) based on the analytical model for the baseline laminate.
248 First, we study the minimum number of runs required to have reliable sensitivity indices
249 for Sobol and FAST methods using the analytical model. Then, we discuss the identified
250 sensitive parameters obtained using the analytical model and a comparison between the
251 three different GSA methods. The total number of runs/model evaluations for Sobol is
252 determined by $N = (n + 2)r$, if second order interaction effects are neglected. Different
253 replication times r are studied to understand the evolution of the SI. Figure 2 (a) and (b)
254 present the evolution of the total SI provided by Sobol and FAST methods, respectively,
255 of the nine input parameters, for increasing number of total runs (N) obtained from the
256 analytical model. Figure 2 (a) also presents a 95% confidence interval (using bootstrap
257 re-sampling) on the Sobol total sensitivity index for all the input parameters. Compared
258 to Sobol, FAST GSA showed stable sensitivity indices at lower values of N. Hence, we
259 selected N=8000 for Sobol and N=5000 for FAST, where the estimators of the statistics
260 stabilized, for the comparative analysis.

261 [Figure 1 about here.]

262 [Figure 2 about here.]

263 Figure 4 (a) and (b) present the comparison of the first order and total order SI of
264 the nine input parameters from the Sobol and FAST GSA methods, respectively, for
265 the selected sample sizes, as discussed above. Figure 5 (a) presents the Morris μ^* vs
266 σ plot for the selected hyper parameters $p=8$ and $r=40$. Figure 5 (b) shows absolute
267 mean values (μ^*) with the 95% confidence interval (obtained through bootstrap re-
268 sampling) on the μ^* for all nine input parameters. All three SA methods provided

269 the same results (comparing Figures 4 and 5) in terms of identifying the sensitive and
270 insensitive parameters. Fiber longitudinal tensile strength (XT) was identified as the
271 most sensitive parameter. All three methods demonstrated that XT has a main effect
272 on the OHT strength and also presents high interactions (high total order SI and high σ
273 in Morris) with the other input parameters. The second sensitive parameter in ranking
274 is the fiber tensile fracture toughness (G°). The third sensitive parameter is the diameter
275 (D) of the specimen hole (when D is varied within its tolerances: 2 ± 0.04 mm), but the
276 effect is seen to be very low. All the other parameters are considered comparatively
277 insensitive towards the OHT strength of the laminate. Even though the agreement
278 between the GSA methods is the same, the total number of model evaluations varies
279 critically for Morris compared to other two methods: 8000, 5000 and 400 total runs for
280 Sobol, FAST and Morris, respectively. Since the GSA was based on an analytical model,
281 the high number of model evaluations are still feasible due to the low computational
282 effort required per model evaluation. Nevertheless, this can be crucial when moving to
283 FE-based high-fidelity numerical models that also incorporate progressive damage.

284 [Figure 3 about here.]

285 5. Sensitivity analysis results: FEM model

286 In this section, we move from analytical based models to FE numerical models
287 to account for the progressive damage evolution and thereby obtaining more reliable
288 strength predictions. In GSA-based FE models, we account for all the material proper-
289 ties (as provided in Table 2), but this can lead to high computational costs per model
290 evaluation. Hence, exploiting the conclusions of the previous study, we incorporate
291 the Morris method with the FE model, due to its capability to screen for insensitive
292 parameters at a relatively low cost. We use the same baseline OHT configuration as
293 explained in the previous section. All the material properties that are inputs to the
294 OHT FE model are considered for the GSA, while the geometrical variables (D and
295 W/D) are not included in the FE-based GSA.

296 Similar to the approach with the analytical model, first we performed the Morris
 297 sensitivity analysis for different hyper parameters to find the optimum p and r values.
 298 Figure 1 presents the Morris plots for the different hyper parameters: different p lev-
 299 els (8, 16 and 32) and r repetitions (5, 10, 20, and 30). We considered 21 material
 300 properties that constitute the elastic, strength and fracture of intra and interlaminar
 301 material systems. Note that GYT and GSL are excluded from the list of input ma-
 302 terial properties for the current sensitivity analysis as these parameters are normally
 303 assumed in the literature as: $GYT = G_{Ic}$ (the matrix tensile fracture toughness is
 304 assumed as the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness) and $GSL = \mathcal{G}_{IIc}$ (the matrix
 305 shear fracture toughness is assumed as mode II interlaminar fracture toughness) due
 306 to the complexity to experimentally characterize them. Each Morris plot in Figure 1
 307 corresponds to N simulations that depend on the value of r , ranging from $N=110$ ($r=5$)
 308 to $N=660$ ($r=30$). The results are seen to be stable at $r=20$, and when r is increased
 309 to 30, the results remain consistent qualitatively. The effect of p was not found to be
 310 as significant as compared to r , and in addition, the computational cost is decided by
 311 r . Hence, we selected $p=16$ and $r=20$ as the hyper parameters.

312 Figure 6 (a) presents the Morris μ^* vs σ plot for the selected hyper parameters $p=16$
 313 and $r=20$ for the FEM-based GSA for 21 material properties. Figure 6 (b) shows the
 314 μ^* values for all the material properties along with the 95% confidence interval on the
 315 μ^* values. From Figure 6, all 21 material properties are placed diagonally in the plot,
 316 with five being placed in the region of high overall effect on output and high interaction
 317 with the other parameters. The remaining parameters that lie in the region with low
 318 values of μ^* and σ are considered insensitive. Fiber longitudinal tensile strength (XT)
 319 and fiber tensile fracture toughness (GXT) are two of the five sensitive parameters
 320 that influence the OHT strength. Both these parameters are characteristic fiber tensile
 321 properties that play a crucial role in a tensile test. Analytical model based GSA also
 322 deemed these two parameters as the most sensitive. In the framework of cohesive law,
 323 XT defines the onset of failure and GXT is the area under the stress-crack opening
 324 curve. Apart from these two anticipated properties, the cohesive law parameters are

Figure 1: Comparison of Morris sensitivity analysis plots for different p and r values for the OHT response obtained from FEM simulations for the baseline laminate case.

325 observed as key properties that affect the OHT strength. f_{XT} and f_{GT} are the ratios
326 of XT and GXT , respectively, in the first branch of longitudinal tensile cohesive law
327 that define the shape of the cohesive law. This is in line with the findings from Maimí
328 et al. [40], where they concluded that the first part of the cohesive law plays a major
329 role in the strength of the OHT specimens.

330 [Figure 4 about here.]

331 6. Morris analysis results: Different case studies

332 OHT strength is strongly influenced by the test configurations such as the specimen
333 geometry and the layups [7]. Hence, in addition to the baseline OHT configuration
334 studied above, we employ the same sensitivity analysis approach to the other case
335 studies. We used the selected Morris hyper parameters identified in the previous section
336 along with all the 23 material properties (Note that GYT and GSL are included in this
337 GSA due to several laminate configurations studied in this section being different from
338 the baseline) detailed in Table 2. With the above-defined values, the sensitivity analysis
339 of each configuration requires 480 simulations ($n=23$, $r=20$ and $p=16$).

340 6.1. Clustering of plies

341 The first case focuses on laminates with different levels of clustered plies. Figure 7
342 (a), (b) and (c) present the Morris sensitivity plots for laminates with one (Lx1), two
343 (Lx2) and four (Lx4) plies clustered. Figure 7 (d) shows the OHT strength from 480
344 model evaluations (each point represents OHT strength obtained from the i^{th} simula-
345 tion) for the different cases studied for ply clustering. For Lx1, the same five properties
346 (as found with the baseline configuration) are observed to be sensitive. But with in-
347 creased ply blocking, mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (\mathcal{G}_{IIc}) shows a higher
348 interaction (σ) with the other parameters and also a higher total effect (μ^*) on OHT
349 strength. These results are in line with the literature, as when plies are clustered,
350 delamination becomes a dominant failure mode [12], and hence \mathcal{G}_{IIc} is seen to have a

351 greater effect on the OHT strength as this parameter is associated with the delami-
352 nation propagation. Blocked plies are prone to have early induced transverse matrix
353 cracks at the vicinity of the hole and free edge, which then grow into delaminations at
354 the interfaces, and hence have lower OHT strength compared to unblocked plies (Figure
355 7 (d)).

356 [Figure 5 about here.]

357 6.2. Notched hole size effect

358 We considered different specimen configurations where the diameter of the hole is
359 increased but the W/D ratio of the specimen is kept as 6 and the same stacking sequence
360 as the baseline laminate is maintained. Figure 8 (a), (b) and (c) present the Morris
361 sensitivity analysis results of specimens with hole sizes of $D=0.5$, $D=2$ and $D=6$ mm,
362 respectively. With the same W/D ratio, the former refers to a small specimen and the
363 latter to a larger specimen. Figure 8 (d) shows the OHT strength from 480 simulations
364 for the different notch size specimens. For the smallest specimen, only XT and \mathcal{G}_{IIc}
365 are the sensitive parameters, with all the other parameters being completely insensitive.
366 With increased hole diameters or larger specimens, fiber fracture toughness (GXT) and
367 the cohesive law parameters (fXT and fGT) move to the right of the plot.

368 In the literature, this is explained as the size effect of the hole, where in smaller
369 specimens, the fracture process zone (FPZ) extends to the edge of the specimen in
370 comparison to the larger specimens where the FPZ is confined to the vicinity of the
371 hole [39]. In fact, for the smallest specimen ($D=0.5$), in fact, the FPZ is larger than the
372 specimen width and the average stress at the fracture plane tends to the unnotched
373 strength of the laminate. Hence only XT is found dominant and none of the cohesive
374 law parameters are found in the sensitive region (Figure 8 (a)). For the other two cases
375 ($D=2$ and $D=6$), FPZ is developed and thus cohesive law parameters are also sensitive.
376 Compared to a smaller specimen, the largest specimen has a smaller FPZ in terms of
377 specimen width and hence the average stress acting on the fracture plane is lower. This

378 is why the OHT strength is higher for D-2 when compared to D-6, as seen in Fig. 8
379 (d).

380 [Figure 6 about here.]

381 *6.3. Different Width to Diameter ratios*

382 We studied specimens with different W/D ratios by varying the hole diameter but
383 keeping the width constant in all cases. The layup is the same as that of the baseline
384 laminate. Four configurations were studied where the specimen with the highest W/D
385 ratio refers to a smaller hole and vice versa. Figure 9 (a), (b), (c) and (d) present the
386 Morris sensitivity results of specimens with W/D ratios 9, 6, 3 and 1.5, respectively. In
387 all the cases, the same five sensitive parameters identified for the baseline configuration
388 are repeated here. For a high W/D ratio specimen, the edge of the hole is very close
389 to the specimen's free edge and hence the damage is more brittle [7]. Hallet et al. [13]
390 reported that for a high W/D ratio specimen, failure can be more pull-out dominant
391 than delamination. In fact, this is seen in the sensitivity analysis results where \mathcal{G}_{IIc} is
392 comparatively less significant for WD-9 (Figure 9 (a)) compared to other smaller W/D
393 ratios.

394 [Figure 7 about here.]

395 *6.4. Laminate stacking configuration*

396 As a last case, we studied three different laminate stacking configurations ranging
397 from soft (42% of plies oriented in 90°) to quasi-isotropic to hard laminates (42% of plies
398 oriented in 0°). Figure 10 (a), (b) and (c) presents the Morris sensitivity analysis results
399 of soft, quasi-isotropic and hard laminates, respectively. Figure 10 (d) shows the OHT
400 strength of all three laminate configurations studied from 480 model evaluations. In
401 all the cases, the fiber dominated parameters are sensitive irrespective of the laminate
402 configuration. For the soft laminate, where there are more 90° plies, \mathcal{G}_{IIc} is significant
403 compared to other configurations due to delamination favored damage modes. This is

404 a result of the reduced number of plies in the direction of loading and hence can induce
405 transverse matrix cracks that develop into delaminations at the hole vicinity. This can
406 be observed with the matrix tensile fracture toughness parameter (GYT) moving to
407 the left and bottom of the plot when moving from soft to hard laminate configuration.

408 The conclusions from the above case studies demonstrate that the proposed GSA
409 analysis identified the same dependencies which are already reported in the literature.
410 Nevertheless, this adds confidence to the proposed FE-based GSA framework which can
411 be applied to other test configurations with less understanding.

412 [Figure 8 about here.]

413 7. A first rough estimation of the design allowables

414 In this section, we exploit the numerous simulations performed for the Morris anal-
415 ysis (see Figure 8 (d)) to obtain a first estimation of the design allowables on the OHT
416 strengths for different configurations. Figure 11 shows the OHT strength variations for
417 the two configurations of hole size effect ($D=2$ and 6 mm) studied in 6.2. Figure 11
418 provides a box plot and mean of the 480 OHT strengths obtained from the Morris anal-
419 ysis, mean OHT strength from the experiments (taken from [18]), deterministic OHT
420 strength from the FE simulation using nominal values (provided in Table 2), and the
421 A and the B basis design values obtained using 480 simulations following the CMH-17
422 approach [3]. The deterministic numerical OHT strengths for both configurations (543
423 and 445 MPa for $D=2$ and 6 mm, respectively) are predicted well when compared with
424 the experimental data (555 and 438 MPa for $D=2$ and 6 mm, respectively), with a
425 maximum error of 2%.

426 The most widely used design allowables A and B basis values are defined as the
427 as 95% of the lower one-sided confidence bound of the 1st and 10th percentiles of the
428 population, respectively [3]. For the estimation of design allowables following CMH-17
429 approach, firstly the distribution that best fits the data (480 OHT strengths) needs
430 to be studied. For the configuration $D=2$ mm, the OHT strengths did not follow

431 the Weibull, normal or log-normal distribution and so a non-parametric procedure
432 was used to estimate the A and B basis values. For D=6 mm, the OHT strengths
433 followed the normal distribution, and subsequently the basis values were calculated
434 following the CMH-17 tabular data for normal distribution. For more details on these
435 procedures, the reader is referred to the CMH-17 [3]. A (465 and 364 MPa for D=2
436 and 6 mm, respectively) and B (485 and 395 MPa for D=2 and 6 mm, respectively)
437 basis design allowables estimated are around 16% and 11% lower than the experimental
438 OHT strengths, hence leading to conservative fail safe design of aeronautic parts. Note
439 that this is only a first estimation of the design allowables with the sole intention to
440 exploit the various FE results from Morris GSA.

441 [Figure 9 about here.]

442 **8. Prospects of an efficient FEM-based Morris GSA for uncertainty quan-** 443 **tification and management**

444 In the response of composite laminates, it is critical to capture the interaction of
445 damage modes in order to have a good prediction on the failure strength of the laminate.
446 Hence, FEM simulation with constitutive damage models integrated with GSA is seen
447 as one of the best options. The drawback of the computational time of FEM simula-
448 tions can be tackled by using Morris GSA, which provides reliable qualitative sensitive
449 analysis results as demonstrated in this paper. The selected Morris hyper-parameters,
450 despite depending on the non-linearity of the model, can be used as a reference for the
451 GSA of other loading cases of composite laminates. Within the framework of UQM, the
452 conclusions of the GSA are paramount. In the next step, the five identified sensitive pa-
453 rameters can be experimentally characterized by testing more specimens. The following
454 three characterization tests can be performed in the laboratory using a greater number
455 of specimens (18 specimens as per CMH-17 [3]) for a better statistical distribution:
456 Longitudinal tensile test for XT (ASTM D3039M [41]), Double edged notched tensile
457 test [42] or compact tension test [43] for GXT , fXT and fGT , C-ELS (ISO 15114 [44])

458 or ENF (ASTM D7905 [45]) mode II interlaminar test for \mathcal{G}_{IIc} . Further, to propagate
459 the uncertainties, machine learning can be used to predict statistical design allowables,
460 as performed by Furtado et al. [46]. In this step, the insensitive material properties
461 identified from GSA can be kept constant while varying only the five identified sensitive
462 properties to have efficient meta-models for the UQM. The design allowables estimated
463 through this methodology will be compared with the A and B basis values obtained in
464 the section 7.

465 9. Conclusions

466 Aeronautical industries are trying to quantify the various uncertainties associated
467 with composite materials responses. Within the framework of uncertainty quantification
468 and management (UQ&M), the industries aim to obtain statistical design allowables
469 for different composite tests to quantify the confidence on the design and certification
470 processes and structural safety. In this aspect, global sensitivity analysis (GSA) on
471 the response of composite structures is a significant precursor to UQ&M. In this pa-
472 per, we demonstrate an efficient integration of GSA methods with analytical or finite
473 element numerical models accounting for progressive damage models to estimate the
474 sensitive material properties that affect the open hole tensile strength of a composite
475 laminate. In the first step, analytical model based GSA was performed on the baseline
476 configuration and different GSA methods were compared to study their prediction and
477 computational efficiency. In a latter step, the analytical model was replaced by FE high-
478 fidelity models and we proposed a FEM-based Morris sensitivity analysis framework
479 to estimate the sensitive parameters, despite the Morris approach being a qualitative
480 analysis but associated with a relatively low cost. We identified five sensitive material
481 properties, properties (out of 23), that influence the open hole tensile strength of the
482 laminated composites, i.e., the longitudinal tensile strength of the uni-directional ply,
483 the first part of the tensile fiber cohesive law and the mode II interlaminar fracture
484 toughness. Further, the framework was investigated with different case studies (ply
485 clusters, notched hole size, laminate configuration, etc.) to evaluate the efficiency when

486 predicting the sensitive parameters. Finally, a first rough estimation of the design al-
487 lowables was performed exploiting the OHT strengths results obtained from the Morris
488 sensitivity analysis. The next step would be to define a UQ&M analysis framework con-
489 sidering the results from the GSA analysis that will help to reduce the dimensionality
490 of the problem.

491 The proposed FEM-based GSA framework contributes towards an efficient UQ&M,
492 where only the sensitive material properties identified can be considered for a detailed
493 experimental characterization or to construct meta-models for machine learning appli-
494 cations to estimate design allowables. In a nutshell, complementing experimental tests
495 with virtual tests to obtain the design allowables help to move towards a safer and
496 efficient designs with reduced number of tests which, in turn, provides more freedom to
497 the design space, reduced costs and knock-down factors.

498 **Acknowledgments**

499 This work has been conducted within the framework of an ongoing EU Horizon
500 2020 Clean Sky 2 Project TREAL (Thermoplastic material allowable generation using
501 a reliability-based virtual modeling platform). This work has received funding from
502 the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No. 864723. The
503 JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation
504 programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union. The project
505 consortium is formed by Amade-Universitat de Girona, Universidad de Porto, MSC
506 e-Xstream and Airbus.

507 **Data availability**

508 The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at
509 this time due to legal or ethical reasons.

510

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(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Comparison of the total sensitivity index of (a) Sobol and (b) FAST, of nine input parameters, for increasing numbers of runs obtained from OHT analytical method for the baseline laminate case. (Fig 1(a) also presents the 95% confidence interval on the total sensitivity index using bootstrap re-sampling.)

Figure 3: Comparison of Morris sensitivity analysis plots for different p and r hyper parameter values obtained from OHT analytical method for the baseline laminate case.

645 Figure 3 presents the Morris plots for different hyper parameters: different p levels
646 (8, 16 and 32) and r repetitions (5, 10, 20, 40, 80 and 100). Recall that the Morris
647 sample size is determined by $N = (n + 1)r$, and to determine the fewest sample runs
648 to obtain effective Morris screening, it is important to inspect the results for different
649 values of the hyper parameters. Increasing r leads to higher numbers of runs/model
650 evaluations ($N=50$ for $r=5$ to $N=1000$ for $r=100$), whereas increasing p denotes a
651 finer discretization of the grid levels in the input domain. Overall, the results from
652 the Morris plots for different p and r values show good consistency (see Figure 3). The
653 most sensitive parameter, XT , and the second most important, G° , (according to the μ^*
654 values) are identified in all the cases, hence we select $p=8$ and $r=40$ (since the variation
655 in the results is negligible among all the cases) as hyper parameters to compare against
656 the other two GSA methods. Note that the Morris sensitivity measures cannot be
657 compared quantitatively between the different Morris plots.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: First order and total order sensitivity indices of OHT analytical response obtained using (a) Sobol (N=8000) and (b) FAST (N=5000) sensitivity analysis for the baseline laminate case.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: (a) Morris sensitivity analysis plot for the selected Morris hyper-parameters ($p=8$ and $r=40$) and (b) Morris absolute mean values with the 95% confidence interval obtained using bootstrapping re-sampling, for the OHT analytical response of the baseline laminate case.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: (a) Morris sensitivity analysis for the selected case ($p=16$, $r=20$) and (b) Morris plot with 95% confidence interval on the absolute mean values obtained through bootstrapped re-sampling, for the baseline laminate case using the OHT FEM approach.

Figure 7: Morris sensitivity analysis plots obtained from FEM simulations for laminates with different levels of ply clusters where (a), (b) and (c) have one, two and four plies clustered, respectively. (Refer to Table 3 for the definition of the ply clustering case study). (d) presents the OHT strength obtained for each case from 480 simulations (each point represents the OHT strength obtained from the i^{th} simulation).

Figure 10: Morris sensitivity analysis plots obtained from FEM simulations for different laminate stacking sequence configurations: (a) Soft laminates, (b) quasi-isotropic laminates and (c) hard laminates (refer to Table 6 for the definition of the different laminate stacking sequences). (d) presents the OHT strength obtained for each case from 480 simulations (each point represents the OHT strength obtained from the i^{th} simulation).

Figure 11: Comparison of OHT strengths (experimental mean (taken from [18]), deterministic numerical OHT strength (using), mean of 480 GSA simulations, B basis design allowable (estimated using 480 GSA simulation following CMH-17 approach) and the box plot of 480 simulations showing the variation in OHT strengths) for two different OHT configurations (D=2 and 6 mm, keeping a constant W/D ratio of 6) studied in 6.2.

Table 1: Input parameters (mean and coefficient of variations of IM7/8552 also provided [39]) for the analytical model based sensitivity analysis

Notation	Input parameter	Mean	Unit	Cov (%)
E_{11}	Young's Modulus in fiber direction	171.42	GPa	1.39
E_{22}	Young's Modulus in matrix direction	9.08	GPa	1.03
ν_{12}	Poissons ratio in 1-2 plane	0.32	-	6.18
ν_{21}	Poissons ratio in 2-1 plane	0.487	-	2.2
G_{12}	Shear modulus in the 1-2 plane	5290	MPa	2.53
XT	Fiber longitudinal tensile strength	2323.5	MPa	5.8
G°	Fiber tensile fracture toughness	133.3	KJ/m ²	5
D	Hole diameter	2	mm	2
W/D	width-to-diameter ratio	6	mm	2

Table 2: Input parameters (means and coefficient of variations of IM7/8552 also provided [39]) for the FEM based sensitivity analysis

Notation	Input parameter	Mean	Unit	Cov(%)
E_{11}	Young's Modulus in fiber direction	171.42	GPa	1.39
E_{22}	Young's Modulus in matrix direction	9.08	GPa	1.03
ν_{12}	Poissons ratio in 1-2 plane	0.32	-	6.18
ν_{23}	Poissons ratio in 2-3 plane	0.487	-	2.2
G_{12}	Shear modulus in the 1-2 plane	5290	MPa	2.53
XT	Fiber tensile strength	2323.5	MPa	5.8
fXT	Ratio of the first branch of tensile cohesive law	0.4	-	8
XC	Fiber compressive strength	1200.1	MPa	12.1
fXC	Ratio of the first branch of compressive cohesive law	0.2	-	8
YT	Matrix tensile strength	62.3	MPa	8.5
YC	Matrix compression strength	253.7	MPa	10.2
SL	Matrix shear strength	92.3	MPa	3.1
GXT	Fiber tensile fracture toughness	133.3	KJ/m ²	5
fGT	Ratio of GXT dissipated in the first branch	0.3	-	8
GXC	Fiber compression fracture toughness	61	KJ/m ²	2
G_{Ic}	Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness	0.28	KJ/m ²	5
GYT	Matrix tensile fracture toughness	0.28	KJ/m ²	5
GYC	Matrix compressive fracture toughness	1.31	KJ/m ²	2
G_{IIc}	Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness	0.79	KJ/m ²	18
GSL	Matrix shear fracture toughness	0.79	KJ/m ²	18
$Coh - t3$	Strength in pure mode I	62.3	MPa	5
$Coh - t1$	Strength in pure mode II	92.3	MPa	5
$Coh - Bk$	B-K exponent parameter for mixed mode propagation	1.45	-	10

Table 3: Case study: Ply clustering

Laminate	Stacking sequence	Laminate thickness (mm)
Lx1	$[45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_S$	4.16
Lx2	$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_S$	4.16
Lx4	$[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_S$	4.16

Table 4: Case study: Notched hole size

Laminate	Hole Diameter (D) (mm)	Specimen width (W) (mm)	Specimen length (L) (mm)	W/D ratio
D-0.5	0.5	3	6	6
D-2	2	12	24	6
D-6	6	36	72	6

Table 5: Case study: Different width-to-diameter ratios

Laminate	Hole Diameter (D) (mm)	Specimen width (W) (mm)	Specimen length (L) (mm)	W/D ratio
WD-9	1.33	12	24	9
WD-6	2	12	24	6
WD-3	4	12	24	3
WD-1-5	8	12	24	1.5

Table 6: Case study: Laminate configurations

Laminate	Stacking sequence	% Plies $[0^\circ / \pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ]$
L-QI	$[45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_S$	$[25/50/25]$
L-Hard	$[45/0/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/0/-45/0]_S$	$[42/50/8]$
L-Soft	$[45/90/-45/90/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/90]_S$	$[8/50/42]$